

Global Joint Ventures

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The variable Joint venture strategic alliance deals bn PPP\$ GDP measures the quantity and size of joint venture agreements and strategic alliances in relation to a country's gross domestic product (GDP), expressed in billions of dollars in terms of purchasing power parity (PPP). A joint venture is a form of cooperation between two or more companies that decide to pool resources, expertise, or markets to pursue common goals, while a strategic alliance refers to a less formalized partnership with similar objectives. The use of GDP in purchasing power parity (PPP) allows for comparing the economic capacity between countries with different price structures, making the data more internationally comparable. This variable helps assess how open a country is to international cooperation through investments and commercial partnerships. Higher values indicate a greater level of economic cooperation through these types of agreements. This variable is important because it reflects a country's ability to attract foreign investments and establish strategic economic collaborations, which are crucial elements for stimulating economic growth, fostering innovation, and gaining access to new markets. It also indicates a higher level of integration into global economic networks, facilitating the transfer of technology and knowledge. Measuring these agreements in relation to GDP helps to understand how these activities impact the national economy in proportion to its size, providing an overview of the relative importance of economic alliances in the global context. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Joint Ventures on a Global Level in 2022. The analysis of data related to joint venture agreements in 2022 reveals a complex picture of international economic cooperation, highlighting the diversity of economies that actively participate in these strategic collaborations. Joint ventures serve as a crucial tool for economic expansion, innovation, and the transfer of expertise between countries and businesses. The analysis of these figures provides interesting insights into how different countries position themselves in this arena. Canada and Malta, both with a score of 100, emerge as absolute leaders in this context. This can be attributed to their ability to attract investments and establish advantageous international collaborations, thanks to a favorable regulatory environment and a strategic position in global markets. Malta, in particular, has built a reputation as a hub for the financial and technology sectors, while Canada, with its diversified economy and open policies towards foreign investments, continues to attract international capital. Israel, with a score of 90.9, is a relevant example of a small country with a high level of technological innovation, particularly in the cybersecurity and advanced technology sectors. Joint ventures in Israel are often driven by the need to share knowledge and resources with foreign partners, especially in strategic markets like the United States and Europe. Sweden, with a score of 81.3, reflects the dynamism of the Nordic economies, characterized by high levels of innovation and economic openness. Joint ventures in Sweden are often concentrated in the green technology and renewable energy sectors, where the country is a global leader. The United States, with 75.5, continues to be a dominant player in the

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global joint venture landscape, even though its score is relatively lower compared to other advanced economies. This could be explained by the tendency of U.S. companies to prefer acquisitions or mergers rather than equal partnerships, while still remaining an attractive hub for international collaborations, especially in the technology and manufacturing sectors. Singapore (71.5) and Hong Kong (65), two major financial centers in Asia, demonstrate their ability to attract joint ventures due to their strategic position in both Asian and global markets. These two countries offer advanced infrastructure and favorable tax regimes, making them ideal centers for foreign investments and alliances between companies from different parts of the world. Switzerland (58.5), famous for its economic and political stability, remains a privileged partner for joint ventures, particularly in the finance, technology, and pharmaceutical research sectors. Similarly, Australia (58.1) stands out as a popular destination for international investments, with a robust economy and business-friendly policies. Cyprus (57.4) and Luxembourg (57.2) are both known for their status as tax havens, which partly explains their high scores. These countries attract joint ventures and other international cooperation agreements thanks to flexible regulations and low taxes, offering a favorable environment for companies seeking to minimize operating costs. The United Kingdom (56.3) and the United Arab Emirates (55.2) remain two important global players. Despite the uncertainty related to Brexit, the United Kingdom continues to be one of the most open economies for joint ventures, particularly in the financial services sector. The United Arab Emirates, with its rapid development and advanced infrastructure, attracts joint ventures in the energy, technology, and tourism sectors. The presence of smaller countries like Iceland (54.2), Bahrain (48.1), and Estonia (34.8) on the list underscores that it is not only large economies that benefit from joint ventures. These countries, despite having relatively small economies, have developed niche markets in specific sectors that make them attractive for international cooperation. Estonia, for example, is a global leader in digital technologies and e-government, while Iceland has leveraged its natural resources and geographical position to attract joint ventures in the energy sector. On the other hand, large economies such as Germany (19.3) and France (20.3) show relatively low scores. This may be due to the fact that many companies in these countries prefer to operate independently or through acquisitions rather than joint ventures. However, these countries remain important centers for economic cooperation, and their participation in joint ventures is often focused on specific sectors such as engineering and automotive industries. Another interesting aspect is the presence of emerging and developing countries at the lower end of the list, such as China (6.7), Brazil (4.7), India (15.8), and South Africa (14.3). Despite their economic weight, these countries show relatively low scores, indicating that joint ventures may not be the primary mode of economic cooperation for them, or that they may face regulatory and bureaucratic obstacles that limit the creation of such agreements. However, countries like India and China are seeking to increase their attractiveness for foreign investments, which could lead to growth in joint ventures in the near future. Finally, it is important to note that countries with more fragile or conflict-ridden economies, such as Iraq (0.7) and Angola (1.5), present extremely low scores. This reflects the significant challenges they face in terms of economic stability and attractiveness for foreign investments. However, with improvements in political and economic conditions, these countries could also see an increase in joint venture opportunities in the future. In conclusion, the data on joint ventures in 2022 reveals an increasingly interconnected world, where both advanced and emerging economies are seeking to leverage strategic alliances to enhance their global competitiveness. Countries with investment-friendly policies, economic stability, and a strong presence in specific sectors tend to be the main beneficiaries of these collaborations. However, there are notable differences between various countries, and the future of joint ventures will largely depend on how nations address global economic challenges and improve their business environments to attract further strategic partnerships.

Global Joint Ventures Between 2013 and 2022. Joint ventures represent a collaborative approach where two or more entities form a common enterprise to achieve specific goals. By analyzing data on joint ventures between 2013 and 2022, we can observe a series of interesting trends across geographic and sectoral dimensions, with significant variations between countries. These changes reflect economic, political, and market dynamics that have impacted each nation differently. Starting with countries that have recorded significant growth, we can focus on those with particularly high percentage variations before moving on to those that have seen a reduction in joint ventures. At the top of the rankings, we find Pakistan, which experienced a 620% growth in joint ventures from 2013 to 2022, increasing from an initial value of 1.5 to 10.8. This exponential increase could be attributed to several factors, including Pakistan's growing integration into the global economy and the rise in foreign direct investment. For instance, China has heavily invested in Pakistan through the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), which has led to numerous collaborations between local and foreign companies. Similarly, Nigeria saw a 330% increase, rising from 1 to 4.3. This growth can be linked to the expansion of the extractive industries, particularly in the oil sector, and investments from multinational companies interested in the country's natural resources. Another European country that has shown significant growth is Slovakia, with a 257.14% increase, from 0.7 to 2.5. This can be explained by Slovakia becoming an important hub for the automotive industry in Europe, attracting investments from giants like Volkswagen, Kia, and PSA Peugeot Citroën. Iceland also witnessed impressive growth of 207.95%, with a significant rise in joint ventures likely related to the expansion of the renewable energy and geothermal sectors, making the country an attractive destination for investors interested in sustainable technologies. Among the countries that saw positive but less explosive growth, we find Malta (144.5%), Sweden (137.03%), and Portugal (100%). These countries have benefited from economic stability and a favorable regulatory environment, making them attractive to foreign investors. The increase in joint ventures in these nations was likely influenced by their participation in European Union programs and initiatives aimed at promoting economic cooperation and transnational investment. Large economies like Canada and the United States also registered growth in joint ventures, with increases of 96.85% and 96.10%, respectively. These numbers demonstrate that despite their already robust economies and international presence, there is still room for new collaborations. Growth is likely linked to high-tech sectors and the energy industry, particularly renewable energy and technological innovation. On the other hand, many countries have seen a significant decline in joint ventures, suggesting an unfavorable economic or political context. Among the most drastic declines, Egypt recorded an 88.67% drop, decreasing from 30.9 to 3.5. This decline could be attributed to political instability and the prolonged effects of the Arab Spring, which discouraged many foreign investors. Similarly, resource-rich countries like Saudi Arabia and Qatar saw drastic reductions in joint ventures, with declines of 85.09% and 82.90%, respectively. This may be connected to the transition of their economies toward models less dependent on natural resources and increased internal and external competition. Another country that experienced a strong decrease is Brazil, with a 32.86% drop. The economic recession and political crisis that have affected the country in recent years may have discouraged new investments and joint ventures. Similarly, Japan saw a 33.15% reduction, which could be attributed to the economic stagnation that has characterized the country in recent decades, combined with a mature and highly competitive domestic market. Many emerging and developing countries also recorded sharp declines in joint ventures. For example, Uzbekistan suffered a 71.78% decrease, while Vietnam saw a 70.06% drop. These figures can be explained by a combination of factors, including economic transitions toward less open models for foreign investment or increased international competition, which reduced joint venture opportunities. Similarly, African countries such as Mozambique (-45.98%) and Zimbabwe (-46.06%) experienced declines in their joint ventures, likely due to political instability, conflicts, and economic challenges that made it more difficult to attract foreign investors. Another group of countries that saw a

significant decline includes nations that had traditionally been strong attractors of international investments, such as Turkey (-80.19%), China (-54.73%), and Russia (-54.62%). In these cases, factors like geopolitical tensions, economic conflicts, and protectionist policies may have reduced collaboration with foreign partners. An interesting trend emerges when examining Middle Eastern and Gulf countries, where nations like Kuwait (-80.41%), Oman (-83.60%), and Bahrain (-51.90%) saw significant declines in joint ventures. These figures could indicate a structural change in these economies, with a greater emphasis on domestic growth and a reduction in reliance on foreign partners. This aligns with the economic diversification policies that many Gulf countries have adopted in recent years to reduce their dependence on oil exports. In summary, the data shows how joint ventures are strongly influenced by a combination of local and global factors. Countries that have benefited from political stability, economic growth, and expanding industrial sectors have seen an increase in collaborations, while those affected by political instability, economic crises, or protectionist policies have experienced a decline. These changes in joint ventures reflect the dynamic nature of the global economy, where investment opportunities and challenges vary significantly from country to country and over time.

Economic Policies for the Development of Joint Ventures. Economic policies aimed at fostering the development of joint ventures on a global scale represent a complex set of measures designed to incentivize cooperation between companies from different countries. These policies leverage the competitive advantages of each party to create joint value and promote economic growth on a global scale. These initiatives lie at the intersection of commercial law, foreign investment regulation, taxation, and the economic development strategies of individual countries. Joint ventures (JVs) are collaborative agreements between two or more companies that decide to share resources, expertise, and risks to achieve a common goal, often related to entering new markets or launching new products or technologies. One of the main incentives that governments around the world have adopted to promote joint ventures is the establishment of a favorable regulatory framework for foreign investment. This approach can be seen in emerging countries such as China and India, where foreign direct investment (FDI) regulations have been gradually loosened to encourage cooperation between local businesses and foreign multinationals. In these countries, authorities often mandate that foreign investments must be made through joint ventures, ensuring the transfer of technological and managerial skills to local firms, thus fostering accelerated industrial development. These policies play a crucial role in economic development, as they not only attract foreign capital but also facilitate the implementation of advanced know-how, which local companies can use to strengthen their competitiveness. Another key aspect of economic policies supporting joint ventures is the provision of tax incentives. Many governments, aware of the risks and complexities associated with establishing joint ventures, offer tax breaks to companies that choose this form of cooperation. Incentives can range from reductions in corporate income taxes for a set number of years to more specific tax deductions related to investments in research and development (R&D). These tax tools are particularly effective in the technology sector, where innovation requires substantial investment, and cooperation between firms is often necessary to share financial and operational risks. The provision of tax incentives helps make joint ventures more economically attractive by reducing the tax burden and thus increasing the profitability of investments, especially in high-potential sectors such as renewable energy, artificial intelligence, and biotechnology. In addition to fiscal policies, many governments implement preferential financing programs to encourage joint ventures. National or international development banks, such as the World Bank or the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, often offer dedicated credit lines to businesses looking to launch joint ventures in

sectors considered strategic for the economic development of a country or region. These favorable financing terms, often accompanied by public guarantees, enable companies to access capital at low costs, facilitating the creation of new transnational business ventures. Beyond financing, many nations provide support through technical advisory programs, fostering dialogue between companies and the sharing of strategic information, often with the involvement of chambers of commerce and trade associations. Another critical dimension of economic policies for the development of joint ventures concerns the protection of intellectual property. Intellectual property rights protection is essential to ensure that companies involved in a joint venture can freely share their technologies and expertise without fear of unlawful exploitation or loss of competitive advantages. In many cases, joint ventures focus on high-tech and innovation-intensive sectors, where the transfer of know-how and patents can be a key success factor. However, in the absence of a robust legal framework guaranteeing respect for intellectual property rights, companies may be reluctant to collaborate. For this reason, many governments have strengthened patent and copyright regulations, working with international organizations such as the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) to create a secure environment for the development of joint ventures. Besides intellectual property regulation, a key factor for the success of international joint ventures is the stability of the legal and economic environment. Companies tend to avoid countries with high levels of political or economic uncertainty, as these conditions can significantly increase operational risks. In this context, economic policies that ensure macroeconomic stability, such as responsible public debt management, inflation control, and adherence to the rule of law, are crucial to attracting investments and facilitating the creation of joint ventures. Moreover, the reduction of trade barriers through free trade agreements and the simplification of bureaucratic procedures are additional measures that can promote international cooperation between companies. Another strategic aspect of economic policies for promoting joint ventures is human capital development. Collaboration between companies from different countries inevitably requires qualified personnel capable of managing complex operations and integrating skills from different corporate cultures. For this reason, many governments invest in professional training programs aimed at developing the managerial and technical skills needed to operate successfully within joint ventures. These programs can be developed in collaboration with universities, technical institutes, and international organizations and often include specific modules on intercultural skills and conflict management, which are particularly relevant in the context of transnational operations. Finally, a key factor for the development of joint ventures is the ability to access large markets. In this regard, enterprise internationalization policies play a crucial role. Many governments, through their foreign trade agencies, provide assistance to domestic companies looking to expand abroad through joint ventures, offering information on local markets, assistance in finding commercial partners, and logistical and legal support. International free trade agreements and special economic zones are also tools used to foster cooperation between companies from different countries, reducing entry costs into foreign markets and increasing the chances of joint venture success. In summary, economic policies for the global development of joint ventures are characterized by a diverse set of tools aimed at reducing the risks associated with international cooperation, incentivizing the sharing of resources and expertise, and promoting technological transfer and industrial development. These policies include the liberalization of foreign investments, the granting of tax and financial incentives, the protection of intellectual property, the promotion of economic and legal stability, human capital development, and support for business internationalization. Through these tools, governments can create an environment conducive to the establishment of joint ventures, thereby promoting economic growth and innovation on a global scale.

Conclusions. Joint ventures have decreased globally, for the countries considered, between 2013 and 2022, from an average amount of 23.38 units to a value of 18.42 units, representing a decline of -21.21%. Some countries, however, have seen a significant increase in the value of joint ventures between 2013 and 2022, such as Pakistan with +620.00%, Nigeria with +330.00%, Slovakia with +257.14%, Iceland with +207.95%, and Lithuania with +162.86%. On the other hand, there are also countries that have experienced a decrease in the value of joint ventures, such as Saudi Arabia with -85.09%, Armenia with -86.67%, Jordan with -86.70%, Egypt with -88.67%, and North Macedonia with -96.60%.

	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	<i>Pakistan</i>	★ 1,5	☆ 10,8	☆ 9,3	★ 620
	<i>Nigeria</i>	★ 1	☆ 4,3	☆ 3,3	★ 330
	<i>Slovak Republic</i>	★ 0,7	☆ 2,5	☆ 1,8	★ 257,1
	<i>Iceland</i>	☆ 17,6	☆ 54,2	☆ 36,6	★ 208
	<i>Lithuania</i>	★ 3,5	☆ 9,2	☆ 5,7	★ 162,9
Worse Performers	<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	☆ 50,3	☆ 7,5	☆ -42,8	★ -85,1
	<i>Armenia</i>	☆ 24	☆ 3,2	☆ -20,8	★ -86,7
	<i>Jordan</i>	★ 100	☆ 13,3	★ -86,7	★ -86,7
	<i>Egypt, Arab Rep.</i>	☆ 30,9	☆ 3,5	☆ -27,4	★ -88,7
	<i>North Macedonia</i>	★ 82,3	☆ 2,8	★ -79,5	★ -96,6

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